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Dynamics of rice-based cropping systems in the southern transitional zone of Karnataka, India

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Varying potentials of irrigation, processes involved in marketing rice and other crops, and the outbreak of pests/diseases are significant factors that contribute to changes in rice-based cropping systems. Restricted moisture availability during summer invariably favors the cultivation of lightly irrigated crops such as groundnut, vegetables, green gram, and cowpea in place of rice. The recent slump in market prices, which has made rice cultivation less profitable, has motivated farmers to adopt more diversified cropping systems.

To study the dynamics of rice-based cropping systems, we conducted a diagnostic sample survey in 14 *taluk* (villages) of the southern transition zone of Karnataka. Primary data were collected by interviewing 700 farmers from 140 villages selected from 3,123 villages covering 1.3 million ha. Additional data were provided, documented by revenue officials. A comparative study was carried out to document the dynamic pattern of changing areas under rice-based cropping systems from 1985-86 to 1996-97. The reasons for the shift in cropping systems were also studied. Earlier, many researchers had reported on the comparative performance and managerial/manorial requirements of rice-based cropping systems (Sewa Ram and Singh 2000, Gangwar and Yadav 2001, Patil et al 1991). But, literature on the dynamics of rice-based cropping systems is scanty.

Our results indicated that rice area grew by 10% in the initial 4 y, and later stabilized at 0.17 million ha (Table 1). However, in many taluk, such as Hassan, Belur, Shimoga, and Tarikere, a negative growth in rice area was recorded in contrast to Alur, Arakalgud, Channagiri, Honnali, and H.N. Pura, which posted a positive growth. The positive growth was attributed to an increase in irrigation potential, while the negative growth was caused by a short supply of irrigation and increased profitability of growing other crops such as vegetables, maize, and groundnut under limited moisture conditions.

A comparison of areas under rice-based cropping systems (Table 2) revealed that the increase in rice area was mainly due to the increase in area under rice-pulses, rice-fallow, rice-vegetables, and rice-maize systems. The loss of rice area under the

rice-rice system was compensated for by these systems. Among them, rice-pulses and rice-fallow systems were forced upon farmers because of the water shortage during the summer. In an area of 4,500 ha, the rice-vegetables system was popular because of nearness to the market and the good price of vegetables. Although rice-groundnut is a more productive and profitable system under limited moisture, its spread was restricted to

Table 2. Comparison of areas (in 000 ha) under rice-based cropping systems.

System	1985-86	1996-97	Change in area (%)
Rice-rice	67.2	59.6	-7.6
Rice-groundnut	17.1	18.9	+1.8
Rice-pulses	0.7	11.3	+10.6
Rice-fallow	0.4	12.8	+12.4
Rice-vegetables	0.8	4.5	+3.5
Rice-maize	0.6	2.5	+1.9
Total	86.8	109.6	+22.6
Additional summer rice area	67.2	59.6	-7.6
Total rice area	154.0	169.2	+9.4

Table 1. Changing area under rice (ha) from 1985-86 to 1996-97.

Taluk	1985-86	1989-90	1991-92	1996-97	Change over 1985-86 (%)
Alur	5,469	7,176	6,455	7,664	+40.1
Arakalgud	5,790	5,666	9,170	12,496	+115.8
Belur	9,815	7,600	8,410	7,359	-25.0
Bharavathi	25,212	34,800	17,092	24,424	-3.1
Channagiri	14,328	15,300	13,968	23,332	+62.8
Hassan	3,664	6,538	4,532	2,251	-38.6
H.D. Kote	8,429	6,591	4,715	7,590	-9.9
Honnali	12,443	16,300	12,701	16,295	+30.9
H.N. Pura	5,771	8,006	9,954	8,924	+54.6
Hunsur	5,710	6,408	7,967	9,580	+67.8
Periyapatna	2,942	4,375	3,470	3,364	+14.3
Shikaripur	22,918	19,800	21,221	21,106	-7.9
Shimoga	20,410	20,800	22,186	17,326	-15.1
Tarikere	11,159	10,586	9,582	7,543	-32.4
Total	154,060	169,946	151,423	169,254	+9.8